

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF HEAT TRANSFER ENHANCEMENT IN CHANNEL FLOW

Prashant Kumar

M.Tech (Student),

Jagannath Gupta Institute of Engineering & Technology (JNIT), JAIPUR

Abstract:

Objective-This study presents the numerical computation on laminar convection heat transfer in a rectangular channel with Longitudinal Vortex Generator. The use of longitudinal vortex generators in the form of wings and winglets to enhance the heat transfer in the plate heat exchangers is well known. The present study evaluates the potential of a single rectangular winglet and a rectangular winglet pair for heat transfer enhancement in a rectangular channel flow. By providing an obstacle in the form of a single rectangular winglet or rectangular winglet pair which obstructs the primary flow a difference in pressure between the front side and back side is created. This pressure difference drives a secondary flow in a plane transverse to the primary flow. This has the effect of churning the main flow and thus leads to a higher heat transfer rate.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- The comparison of a rectangular channel mounted with single rectangular winglet, a winglet pair and plain rectangular channel at $Re=200$ is done. The performance of the design is evaluated for a rectangular winglet pair with varying height and in the Reynolds number range of 200 to 500 for an angle of attack $\beta = 28.7^\circ$. The level of heat transfer augmentation is quantified in terms of the Nusselt number and the bulk temperature. The fundamental governing equations for incompressible three dimensional laminar flow are considered and Modified MAC Algorithm is used to obtain the numerical solution of the governing equations. While the vortex generator creates a secondary flow it does add to the resistance to the primary flow i.e., a price is to be paid for the heat transfer enhancement in the form of a higher pumping power required to force the fluid across the vortex generator.

Findings- This is evaluated to ensure that the increase in pumping power is moderate. The purpose of heat transfer enhancement techniques is to reduce the size of the heat exchanger for a given heat transfer load. The channel with a winglet pair is more effective as comparison to the single winglet. The heat transfer increases with the increase of the winglet height. The heat transfer increases with the increase in Reynolds number

Scope for further work-The computation has been done assuming the flow regime to be laminar in plate heat exchangers. But in some special application involving high velocity of fluid, the flow regime can become turbulent. Therefore, the present study can be extended for the turbulent flows. Using an appropriate turbulence model, the performance of the purposed design can be computed for high Reynolds number. This study can also be extended for the finite thickness of the winglet pair.

Originality/Value- The paper includes practical examples of organizations following different Professor Strategies and also includes literature review about leadership and talent management, which promotes unique and interesting contributions in research.

Keywords: Numerical Computation , Laminar Convection, Heat Transfer, Winglet

1 INTRODUCTION

Heat exchanger is a device that is used to transfer thermal energy [1] between two or more fluids, at different temperatures and in thermal contact. In heat exchangers, there are usually no external heat and work interactions. Typical application involves heating or cooling of fluid stream of concern and evaporation or condensation of single or multi component fluid streams. A variety of heat exchangers are used in industry and in their products. Heat exchangers are classified according to transfer process, number of fluids, and degree of surface compactness, construction features, flow arrangements, and heat transfer mechanism

In most heat exchanger, heat transfer between fluids takes place through separating walls or into and out of a wall in transient manner. In many heat exchangers the fluids are separated by heat transfer surface and ideally they do not mix or leak. Such exchangers are referred to as direct transfer type. Exchangers in which there is intermittent heat exchange between the hot and cold fluids via thermal energy storage and release through the exchanger surface or matrix are referred to as indirect transfer type. Common examples of heat exchangers are shell and tube exchangers, automobile radiators, condensers, evaporators, air preheaters, and cooling towers. A heat exchanger consist of heat transfer elements such as core or matrix containing the heat transfer surface, and fluid distribution elements such as headers, manifolds, tanks, inlet

And outlet nozzles or pipes, or seals. Usually there are no moving parts in a heat exchanger.

The heat transfer surface is a surface of the exchanger's core that is in direct contact with fluids and through which heat is transferred by conduction. That portion of the surface that is in direct contact with both the hot and cold fluids and transfers heat between them is referred to as the primary or direct surface. To increase the heat transfer area, appendages may be intimately connected to the primary surface to provide an extended, secondary, or indirect surface. These extended surface elements are referred to as fins. Thus, heat is conducted through the fin and convected from the fin (through the surface area) to the surrounding fluid or vice versa. Depending on whether the fin is being cooled or heated. As a result, the addition of fins to the primary surface reduces the thermal resistance on that side and thereby increases the total heat transfer from the surface for the same. Fins may form flow passages for the individual fluids but do not separate the two (or more) fluids of the exchanger. An arbitrary classification can be made, based on the heat transfer surface area/volume ratio, into compact and non compact heat exchangers.

In this study we will only concise to compact heat exchanger to evaluate the performance of heat exchanger.

1.1 COMPACT HEAT EXCHANGER:

Compact heat exchangers [1] are characterized by a large heat transfer surface area per unit volume of the exchanger, resulting in reduced space, weight, support structure and footprint, energy requirements and cost as well as process design, plant layout and processing conditions, together with low fluid inventory. A gas-to fluid exchanger is referred to as a compact heat exchanger if it incorporates a heat transfer surface having a surface area density greater than about $700 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ ($213\text{ft}^2/\text{ft}^3$) and $400 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ ($122\text{ft}^2/\text{ft}^3$) or higher for operating in a liquid or phase-change stream. A laminar flow heat exchanger (also referred to as a mesa heal exchanger) has a surface area density greater than about $3000 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ ($914\text{ft}^2/\text{ft}^3$). A liquid/two-phase fluid heat exchanger is referred to as a compact heat exchanger if the surface area density on any one fluid side is greater than about $400 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$.

An essential component of many of this compact concept is heat and mass transfer enhancement. In this case some of main enhancement methods which are used in the implementation of compact system. Compact heat exchanger is highly efficient, allow greater amount of energy to be recovered between process streams, they are more versatile in terms of the number of process streams that can be handled. Some compact heat exchangers can handle only two streams, other can handle four or more with ease.

Even greater long term importance to the process industries is the ability to use compact heat exchanger manufacturing technology to integrate effective with other unit operations, such as reactor, in one unit.

Compact heat exchangers currently [2] have only a modest share of the process industry heat exchanger market (in order of 5-10%), their proportion of over all sales is growing. Compact heat exchangers sales are increasing at about 10% per annum, in a market where total heat exchangers sales are only rising about 1% per annum.

Compact heat exchanger offer a number of benefits, including

- (a) improved efficiency

- (b) smaller volume & weight
- (c) lower installed cost
- (d) multi-stream & multi pass configuration
- (e) Tighter control of conditions
- (f) Improved safety

In order to be able to evaluate its performance, methods to predict the heat transfer coefficient and pressure drop must be developed. In this direction, CFD is considered an efficient tool for momentum and heat transfer rate estimation in this type of heat exchangers. The type of flow in such narrow passages, which is associated with the choice of the most appropriate flow model for CFD simulation. Generally fluid (gas and liquid) flows are governed by partial differential equations which represent conservation laws for the mass, momentum, and energy. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is the art of replacing such PDE systems by a set of algebraic equations which can be solved using digital computers. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) provides [3] a qualitative (and sometimes even quantitative) prediction of fluid flows by means of

- Mathematical modeling (partial differential equations)
- Numerical methods (discretization and solution techniques)
- Software tools (solvers, pre- and post processing utilities)

1.2 HEAT TRANSFER ENHANCEMENT IN HEAT EXCHANGER

The subject of enhanced heat transfer [4] has developed to the stage that it is of serious interest for heat exchanger application. The refrigeration and automotive industries routinely use enhanced surface in their heat exchangers. Every heat exchanger is a potential candidate for enhanced heat transfer. An “enhanced heat transfer surface” has a special surface geometry that provides a higher ‘hA’ value, per unit base surface area than a plain surface. The term “enhancement ratio” (E_h), is the ratio of the ‘hA’ of an enhanced surface to that of a plain surface. Thus,

$$E_h = \frac{hA}{(hA)_p} \quad (1.1)$$

Consider a two fluid counter flow heat exchanger. The heat transfer rate for a two fluid heat exchanger is given by

$$Q = UA\Delta T_m \quad (1.2)$$

To illustrate the benefits of enhancement, we will multiply and divide equation (12) by the total tube length, L

$$Q = \frac{UA}{L} L\Delta T_m \quad (1.3)$$

The term L/UA is the overall thermal resistance, per unit tube length, and is given by

$$\frac{L}{UA} = \frac{L}{\eta_1 h_1 A_1} + \frac{L t_w}{k_w A_m} + \frac{L}{\eta_2 h_2 A_2} \quad (1.4)$$

Where subscript '1' and '2' refer to fluids 1 and 2, respectively. The term η is the surface efficiency, should extended surface be employed. The performance of the heat exchanger will be enhanced if the term UA/L is increased. An enhanced surface geometry may be used to increase either or both of the hA/L terms, relative to that given by plain surfaces. This will reduce the thermal resistance per unit tube length, L/UA . The reduced L/UA may be used for one of three objectives.

1. Size reduction: If the heat exchange rate (Q) is held constant, the heat exchanger length may be reduced. This will provide smaller heat exchanger.

2. Increased UA: This may be exploited either of two ways:

a. Reduced ΔT_m : if Q and the total tube length (L) are held constant, the ΔT_m may be reduced. This provides increased thermodynamics process efficiency, and yields a savings of operating costs.

b. Increased heat exchange: Keeping L constant, the increased UA/L will result in increased heat exchange rate for fixed fluid inlet temperatures.

3. Reduced pumping power for fixed heat duty, although it may concern surprising that enhanced surface can provide reduced pumping power, this is theoretically possible, however, this will typically require that the enhanced heat exchanger operates at a velocity smaller than the competing plain surface

1.2.1 The Enhancement Techniques

These Techniques are segregated in to two groupings: "passive" and "active" techniques. Passive techniques employ special surface geometries, or fluid additives for enhancement. The active techniques require external power, such as electric or acoustic fields and surface vibration.

1.2.1.1 Active Techniques

(a) Mechanical aids involve stirring the fluid by mechanical means or rotating the surface. Mechanical surface scrapers, widely used for viscous liquids in the chemical process industry, can be applied to duct flow of gases. Equipment with rotating heat exchanger ducts is found in commercial practice.

(b) Surface vibration at either low or high frequency has been used to improve single phase heat transfer. A piezoelectric device may be used to vibrate a surface and impinge small droplets on to a heated surface to promote "spray cooling"

(c) Fluid vibration is the more practical type of vibration enhancement because of the mass of most heat exchangers. The vibration range from pulsations of about 1 HZ to ultrasound. Single phase fluids are of primary concern.

(d) Electrostatic fields (direct current, d.c, or alternating current a.c) are applied in many different ways to dielectric fluids. Generally speaking, electrostatic fields can be directed to cause greater bulk mixing of fluid in the vicinity of the heat transfer surface.

(e) Injection is utilized by supplying gas through a porous heat transfer surface to a flow of liquid or by injecting the same liquid upstream of the heat transfer section

(f) Suction involves vapor removal, in nucleate or film boiling, or fluid withdrawal in single phase flow through a porous heated surface.

(g) Jet impingement forces a single phase fluid normally or obliquely toward the surface. Single or multiple jets may be used, and boiling is possible with liquids.

1.2.1.2 Passive techniques

(a) **Coated surface** involve metallic or nonmetallic coating of the surface. Examples include a non-wetting coating, such as Teflon, to promote drop wise condensation, or a hydrophilic coating that promotes condensate drainage or evaporator's fins, which reduce the wet air pressure drop. A fine scale porous coating may be used to enhance nucleate boiling. Figure 1.7 shows the cross-section of a sintered porous metal coating for nucleate boiling. The particle size is on the order of .0005 mm. These may be used to enhance single phase convection or condensation.

Figure 1.7 cross section of porous boiling surface

(b) **Rough surface** may be either integral to the base surface or made by placing a “roughness” adjacent to the surface. In tegral roughness formed by machining, or “reconstructing” the surface.

Figure 1.8 (a) Tube side roughness for two phase flow, (b) “rough” surface for nucleate boiling

For single phase flow, the configuration is generally chosen to promote mixing in the boundary layer near the surface, rather than to increase the heat transfer area. Figure 1.8 (a) shows two examples of integral roughness. Figure 1.8 (b) shows an enhanced “rough” surface for nucleate boiling

(c) **Extended surface** are employed in many heat exchangers. As shown in equation (14), the thermal resistance may be reduced by increasing the heat transfer coefficient (h), or the surface area (A), either h or A . use of a plate fin may provide only area increase.

Figure 1.9 Enhanced surface for gases (a) offset strip fins used in plate fin heat exchanger, (b) louvers fins used in automotive heat exchanger, (c) segmented fins for circular tubes, (d) integral aluminum strip finned tube, (e) louvers tube and plate fin, (f) corrugated plates used in rotary regenerators

However, formation of a special shape extended surface may also provide increased h . enhancement efforts are directed toward extended surfaces that provide a higher heat transfer coefficient than that of plate fin design. Figure 1.9 shows variety of enhanced extended surface used for gases. The Figure 1.9 (a) through a surface involves repeated formation and destruction of thin form thermal boundary layers. Extended surface for liquids typically use much smaller fin heights than those used for gases. Shorter fin heights are used for liquids, because liquids typically have higher heat transfer coefficient than gases. Use of high fins with liquids would result in poor material utilization. Examples of extended surface for liquids are shown in Figure 1.9

(d) **Displaced inserts** devices are inserted in to flow channel to improve energy transport at the heated surface indirectly. They are used with single and two phase flow. The figure 1.10(a) and (b) devices mix the main flow, in addition to that in the wall region. The figure 1.10 (c) wire coil insert is placed at the edge of boundary layer, and is intended to promote mixing with in the boundary layer, without significantly affecting the main flow.

Figure 1.10 (a) spaced disk device, (b) spaced stream line shaped insert devices, (c) displaced wire coil insert

(e) **Coiled** may provide more compact heat exchangers, secondary

Flow in the coiled tube produces higher single phase coefficients and improvement in most boiling regions. However, a quite small coil diameter is required to obtain moderate enhancement

(f) **Vortex generator** is one of the most important passive techniques having a low aspect ratio (height and length ratio) foil or flat plate having a rectangular or triangular geometry, which can be mounted or punched out on or from the surface of an angle of incidence to the fluid stream. As the fluid flows past vortex generator, flow striking front surface of the winglet results in momentum change. The pressure difference on the either side of the vortex generator will cause the secondary flow. This secondary flow is called as vortex. Various types of vortex generator like wing type and winglet type are used for producing the vortex in flowing fluid in heat exchanger for heat transfer enhancement purpose.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The field of enhancement of heat transfer with active and passive method has been an active area of research in the recent years. This fact can be sustained by the following compilation of the researchers and their contribution to the growth of field. Enhancement of heat transfer using passive vortex generators has been beautifully presented by **Jacobi et al. [5]**. The review presented in this paper will focus on heat transfer enhancement by the use of passive LVG's

Fiebig et al. [6] described the flow structure and heat transfer in channels with wing type vortex generators. Exemplary results of the flow structure in the channel with a pair of punched delta winglets are reported in the paper. Results show that even at large angle of attack (65°) stable vortices are generated. The spiraling motion induced by these vortices can enhance the nusselt number by 52% on an area which is 15 times than the vortex generators area. **Biswas et al. [7]** numerically predicted the structure of flow and heat transfer characteristics in a rectangular channel with a built-in delta wing protruding from the bottom wall. The predictions are made through the numerical solution of complete Navier-Stokes and energy equations. Augmentation of heat transfer between the flowing fluid and channel wall is seen. The effect of a punched hole, beneath the wing-type vortex generator, on the heat transfer and skin friction characteristics has been determined. The influence of the vortex generator's angle of attack and Reynolds number on heat transfer and skin friction is determined. The combined span wise average Nusselt number showed increases as large as 34% even at the exit of a long channel at an angle of attack of 28.7° . **Biswas et al. [8]** numerically investigated the flow structure and heat transfer enhancement in a channel with a built-in circular tube and a winglet type vortex generator. The geometrical configuration represents an element of a gas-liquid fin-tube cross flow heat exchanger. In the absence of the

winglet type vortex generator, relatively little heat transfer takes place in the downstream of the circular tube which is recirculation region with low velocity fluid. However, in the presence of a winglet type longitudinal vortex generator in the wake region behind the cylinder, heat transfer in this region can be enhanced as high as 240%. Results show a marked increase in overall channel heat transfer. The enhancement shows great promise in reducing the size of the heat exchangers. **Deb et al. [9]** presented the heat transfer characteristics and flow structure in laminar and turbulent flows through rectangular channel containing built-in vortex generators by means of solution of the full Navier-Stokes and energy equations. The geometrical configuration of interest is representative of single element of a plate-fin cross-flow heat exchanger. Each winglet-pair induces longitudinal vortices behind it. These vortices swirl the flow around the axis parallel to the main stream direction and strongly enhance the exchange of fluid between the wall and the core region which causes high heat transfer augmentation. **Jacobi et al. [10]** demonstrated a 50% to 60% enhancement of average heat and mass transfer for flow over a flat plate at low Reynolds numbers, using delta-wing vortex generators. The mechanisms responsible for the enhancement are determined, and a single parameter for estimating their effect is established. Using a straightforward method for evaluating this parameter from flow visualization data, optimal delta-wing geometries were found for Reynolds numbers of 600, 800, and 1000 based on wing-chord length. The results were also used to develop a clearer understanding of the interactions between the vortex and boundary layer. When a high-circulation vortex is placed near the edge of the boundary layer, it effectively thins the boundary layer; the vortex advects free-stream fluid into the temperature or species boundary layer. Vortices should be generated in common in flow arrangement so that induced velocities keep the vortices near the boundary layer. **Chen et al. [11]** described the influences of the angle of attack and the aspect ratio of a winglet, which is punched near the leading edge of the fin in a high performance, finned oval tube (FOT), on the heat transfer enhancement (HTE) and flow loss penalty (FLP). Three dimensional flow and conjugate heat transfer in a finned oval tube were calculated for a thermally and hydro dynamically developing laminar flow ($Re = 300$) by solving the Navier Stokes and energy equations with a finite volume method in body fitted grids. The conjugate heat transfer was realized by iterations of the energy equation in the flow field and of the conduction equation in the fin. Three angles of attack ($\beta = 20^\circ, 30^\circ$ and 45°) and two aspect ratios ($A = 1.5$ and 2) were investigated. Velocity and temperature fields, vortex formation, local heat transfer distributions and global results are presented. The winglet with $\beta = 30^\circ$ and $A = 2$ provides the best ratio of HTE to FLP equal to 1.02. **Vasudevan et al. [12]** numerically computed the enhancement potential of triangular fins (which are widely used inserts between the plates of the plate fin heat exchanger) having delta winglets mounted on their slant surfaces. The performance of this combination is evaluated for varying angles of attack of the winglet and different thermal boundary conditions. The performance of the combination of triangular fins and winglets with stamping on the slant surfaces has also been evaluated. **Torri et al. [13]** proposed a novel technique that can augment heat transfer but nevertheless can reduce pressure-loss in an-tube heat exchanger with circular tubes in a relatively low Reynolds number, by deploying delta winglet-type vortex generators. The winglets are placed with a heretofore-unused orientation for the purpose of augmentation of heat transfer. This orientation is called as ‘‘common flow up’’ configuration.

3 PROBLEM FORMULATION

A compact plate heat exchanger is having rectangular channel geometry with a single rectangular winglet and a rectangular winglet pair as shown in Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2. The leading edge of the rectangular winglet type vortex generator is attached at a distance of $2.66H$ along the flow stream. The rectangular channel of height ‘ H ’ and length ‘ L ’ along the flow stream $L=8.4H$. The width of the channel is ‘ $2H$ ’. The vortex generator in the form of rectangular winglet and rectangular winglet pair is mounted on the bottom surface $ABB'A'$ of the channel as shown in Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4. The distance between the winglet pair is $0.23H$.

Figure 3.1 Rectangular channel with a single rectangular winglet

Figure 3.2 Rectangular channel with rectangular winglet pair

Figure 3.3 Top view of the bottom surface of the channel with a rectangular winglet

Figure 3.4 Top view of the bottom surface of the channel with a pair of rectangular winglet

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The fundamental governing equations for incompressible three dimensional laminar flow viz. continuity, momentum and energy equations are considered in non-dimensional conservative form.

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial Y} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial Z} = 0 \quad (4.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\partial(U)}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial(UV)}{\partial Y} + \frac{\partial(UX)}{\partial Z} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial X} + \frac{1}{R_e} \left[\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial Y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial Z^2} \right] \quad (4.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tau} + U \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial Y} + W \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial Z} = \frac{1}{R_e P_r} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial Y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial Z^2} \right] \quad (4.3)$$

In the above equations, velocities have been non-dimensionalized by the average incoming velocity U_{av} at the channel inlet, all lengths have been dimensionlized with channel height 'H' and pressure with ρU_{av}^2 . The Reynolds number is given by

$$R_e = \frac{U_{av} H}{\nu} \quad (4.4)$$

The symbol ν being the kinematic viscosity of the fluid. Air (Pr=0.71) is the working fluid and the flow regime is taken to be laminar. The dimensionless temperature θ is defined as

$$\theta = \frac{(T - T_w)}{(T_w - T_\infty)} \quad (4.5)$$

Where T_w is the temperature of the wall T_∞ is the temperature of the incoming fluid.

4.2 BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Boundary conditions in these investigations: At the top and bottom surface

$$U = V = W = 0; T = T_w \quad (4.6)$$

For side wall (Plane of Symmetry)

$$W = \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial Z} \right) = \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial Z} \right) = \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial Z} \right) = 0 \quad (4.7)$$

At the entrance to channel

$$U = U(Y), V = W = 0, T = T_\infty \quad (4.8)$$

At the exit Orlanski [21] boundary conditions are given by

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial \tau} + U_c \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial X} = 0 \quad (4.9)$$

Where ϕ is the dependent variable on U, V, W. The quantity U_c is the main channel outflow velocity. No slip velocity boundary conditions and constant wall temperature conditions are taken for the obstacle.

4.3 GRID SYSTEM USED

The region in which computation are to be performed is divided in to a set of small cells of edge lengths δx , δy , and δz . The mesh size is taken 60X15X26. Where 60 refers to the grids in x direction, 15 in y direction and 26 in z direction. With respect to this set of computations cells, velocity components are defined at the centre of cell faces to which they are normal. The pressure and temperature are defined at the centre of the cell.

Another important advantage of such grid system is that the transport rates across the Faces of the control volumes can be computed without interpolation of velocity component.

Figure 4.1 Staggered Grid arrangement

4.4 SOLUTION PROCEDURE

1. The unsteady N-S equation for incompressible fluid flow and the continuity equations are the governing equations.

2. The solution is marched in the time direction. A modified version of Marker and Cell (MAC) method by [22, 23] is used to obtain the numerical solution of the governing equations. The MAC algorithm is given in reference [24]. In the staggered grid arrangement used the velocities are not defined at the nodal points but whenever required, they are to be found by interpolation, for example, with uniform grids, we can write

$$U_{i+1/2,j,k} = \frac{1}{2} \left[U_{i+1,j,k} + U_{i,j,k} \right] \quad (4.10)$$

Where a product or a square of quantity appears, it is to be averaged first and then the product is to be formed.

The Convective terms of the momentum equation are discretized using a weighted average of second upwind and space centered scheme. The diffusive terms are discretized by central difference scheme. Some of the discretized terms are as:

$$\frac{\partial(U^2)}{\partial X} = \frac{1}{4\delta X} \left[(U_{i,j,k} + U_{i,j,k})(U_{i,j,k} - U_{i,j,k}) \right] + \alpha \left| U_{i,j,k} + U_{i+1,j,k} \right| \left| U_{i,j,k} + U_{i+1,j,k} \right| - (U_{i-1,j,k} + U_{i,j,k}) - \alpha \left| (U_{i-1,j,k} + U_{i,j,k}) \right| \left| (U_{i-1,j,k} - U_{i,j,k}) \right| = DUUDX \quad (4.11)$$

$$\frac{\partial(UV)}{\partial Y} = \frac{1}{4\delta Y} \left[(V_{i,j,k} + V_{i+1,j,k})(U_{i,j,k} - U_{i,j+1,k}) \right] + \alpha \left| (V_{i,j,k} + V_{i+1,j,k}) \right| \left| (U_{i,j,k} - U_{i,j+1,k}) \right| - (V_{i,j-1,k} + V_{i+1,j-1,k})(U_{i,j-1,k} + U_{i,j,k}) - \alpha \left| (V_{i,j-1,k} + V_{i+1,j-1,k}) \right| \left| (U_{i,j-1,k} - U_{i,j,k}) \right| = DUVDX \quad (4.12)$$

$$\frac{\partial(UW)}{\partial Z} = \frac{1}{4\delta Z} \left[(W_{i,j,k} + W_{i+1,j,k})(U_{i,j,k} - U_{i,j,k+1}) \right] + \alpha \left| (W_{i,j,k} + W_{i+1,j,k}) \right| \left| (U_{i,j,k} - U_{i,j,k+1}) \right| - (W_{i,j,k-1} + W_{i+1,j,k-1})(U_{i,j,k-1} + U_{i,j,k}) - \alpha \left| (W_{i,j,k-1} + W_{i+1,j,k-1}) \right| \left| (U_{i,j,k-1} - U_{i,j,k}) \right| = DUWDX \quad (4.13)$$

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial X} = \frac{P_{i+1,j,k} - P_{i,j,k}}{\delta X} = DPDX \quad (4.14)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial X^2} = \frac{U_{i+1,j,k} - 2U_{i,j,k} + U_{i-1,j,k}}{(\delta X)^2} = D2UDX2 \quad (4.15)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial Y^2} = \frac{U_{i,j+1,k} - 2U_{i,j,k} + U_{i,j-1,k}}{(\delta Y)^2} = D2UDY2 \quad (4.16)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial Z^2} = \frac{U_{i,j,k+1} - 2U_{i,j,k} + U_{i,j,k-1}}{(\delta Z)^2} = D2UDZ2 \quad (4.17)$$

With , If $\alpha=1$, the scheme becomes second upwind (4.18)

If $\alpha=0$ it becomes space centered Factor α is chosen in such a way that the differencing scheme retains “something” of second order accuracy and the required up winding is done for the sake of stability. The value of α is taken 0.2.

3. With the help of momentum equation a provisional value of velocity component is computed explicitly at next time step. This converged solution in space domain may not be the solution of the problem.

4. The explicitly advanced velocity components may not be divergence free. Hence it is not a real flow field. With these velocity components the continuity equation is evaluated in each cell. If the non-zero value is obtained, means there is some mass accumulation which is not physically possible. Hence it is an incorrect pressure field. So the pressure at any cell is directly linked with the value of $(\nabla \cdot u)$ at that cell

5. On one hand pressure are corrected & on other hand the velocity components have adjusted.

6. Now the correction procedure is done through iterative cycle till a divergence free velocity field is reached with a prescribed upper bound; here a value of 0.0001 is taken.

7. After evaluating the steady state velocities, the energy equation is solved with a successive. Over relaxation technique to determine the temperature field. This steady state energy equation, neglecting the dissipation term, may be written in the following conservative form as

$$\frac{\partial U\theta}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial V\theta}{\partial Y} + \frac{\partial W\theta}{\partial Z} = \frac{\nabla^2\theta}{P_e} \quad (4.19)$$

Equation 3.20 may be rewritten as

$$\nabla^2\theta = P_e [CONVT]_{i,j,k}^m \quad (4.20)$$

$$\frac{\theta_{i+1,j,k} - 2\theta_{i,j,k} + \theta_{i-1,j,k}}{(\delta X)^2} + \frac{\theta_{i,j+1,k} - 2\theta_{i,j,k} + \theta_{i,j-1,k}}{(\delta Y)^2} + \frac{\theta_{i,j,k+1} - 2\theta_{i,j,k} + \theta_{i,j,k-1}}{(\delta Z)^2} = S^{*m} \quad (4.22)$$

Where $S^{*m} \equiv P_e [CONVT]_{i,j,k}^m$

This equation is solved by the SOR method with the right hand side being updated after each iterative sweep

5 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The computation are carried out in rectangular channel of length $L= 8.4H$ at Reynolds number, $Re = 200$ with longitudinal at an angle of attack $\beta = 28.7^\circ$. The velocity and temperature of the laminar channel flow with LVG in the form of rectangular winglet and a rectangular winglet pair has been computed. The comparison between the single rectangular winglet, rectangular winglet pair and plain channel has been predicted with the help of flow structure and heat transfer.

5.1 FLOW STRUCTURE

The secondary flow pattern along and behind the single rectangular winglet, rectangular winglet pair in a channel at Reynolds number, $Re = 200$ and $\beta = 28.7^\circ$ is shown in Figure 5.1 and 5.2.

Figure 5.1 Cross stream velocity vectors at different locations along stream wise direction for single rectangular winglet at $Re = 200$ and $\beta = 28.7^\circ$

The plots show the generation of vortices. The vortices generated because of the pressure difference between front and back side of the obstacle. These vortices cause the fluid to churn. This churning motion causes the hot fluid near the wall flow in the core region and vice versa. This leads to a higher heat transfer rate. In case of rectangular winglet pair to counter rotating vortices are generated which disturb the more region under consideration than in case of single rectangular winglet. So the mixing of the fluid is more in case of winglet pair than single winglet

5.2 HEAT TRANSFER

The bulk temperature along the axial direction for a rectangular channel with a single winglet, a winglet pair and plain channel at $Re = 200$ and $\beta = 28.7^\circ$ is shown in Figure 5.2. It is observed that as the fluid stream moves along the axial direction, there is an increase in bulk temperature because of the mixing of the fluid due to formation of vortices in case of a rectangular winglet and winglet pair.

In order to quantify the heat transfer performance, the combined span wise nusselt number can be computed by taking the average of the local nusselt number along the periphery of the rectangular channel. The variation of Nu_{sa} along the axial is shown in figure 5.3. The nusselt number is high in the entrance region, the real effect is seen behind the vortex region. The Figure shows that Nu_{sa} for the winglet pair is more at any axial location behind the trailing edge of the obstacle than single winglet or the channel without winglet. So the heat transfer enhancement of a winglet pair is more than a single winglet and plain duct

Figure 5.2 Variation of bulk temperature along the channel

Figure 5.3 Variation of spanwise average Nusselt number along the channel

Figure 5.4 Pressure variation along the channel

While the employment of winglet enhances the heat transfer rate there is a price to pay in the form of additional pumping power required to force the fluid across the exchanger with a vortex generator. The magnitude of this

increase can be had by comparing the overall pressure drop across the channel for the case of plane channel to that of the channel provided with a single winglet and a winglet pair.

For this purpose the average pressure at any section was determined through the ratio of the area integral of pressure at that section to the cross sectional area. Figure 5.4 shows that the pressure drop is abrupt where the obstacle is placed.

5.3 Effects of various parameters on heat transfer enhancement for the case of winglet pair

It has been concluded from above comparison that the heat transfer enhancement for rectangular winglet pair is more. The effect of two parameters is studied in this chapter

(1) Variation of height of the rectangular winglet.

(2) Variation of Reynolds number.

5.3.1 Variation of height of the rectangular winglet.

The heat transfer rate is also different for winglet pair with reference to height. Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6 shows the variation of bulk temperature and combined spanwise average Nusselt number distribution along the rectangular channel with rectangular winglet pair for the Reynolds number $Re = 200$ and an angle of attack $\beta = 28.7^\circ$ at different heights of the winglet pair. The study shows that as the height of rectangular winglet is increase from $h_1=0.333H$ to $h_1=0.5994H$, the rise in bulk temperature is clearly visible in the downstream.

Figure 5.5 Variation of bulk temperature

Figure 5.6 Variation of span average Nusselt number

This can be explained as when height of V.G (h_1) is increased, the cross-sectional flow area of the channel decreases and the fluid velocity at the side edge of the obstacle increases for the same volume flow rate, so the strength of the vortices is increased hence improving the heat transfer. The combined spanwise average Nusselt number increases by 50% at $X=5.18H$ as the winglet pair height is increase from $h_1=0.333H$ to $h_1=0.5994H$. So the heat transfer increases with the increase in height of the rectangular winglet.

5.3.2 Variation of Reynolds number

To examine the effect of Reynolds number with constant angle of attack $\beta = 28.7^\circ$ for the case of winglet pair, the computation are carried out at $Re = 200, 400$ and 500 . Figure shows 4.8 and Figure 4.9 shows the results for different Reynolds number.

Figure 5.7 illustrate that as the value of Re is increase; the bulk temperature distribution along the channel is coming down. This is because, the lowering in Re

Lowers the stream velocity and it provides to fluid to spend more time at a particular location, cause gain in more amount of heat. But, Figure 5.7 shows that, corresponding increase in Nusselt number with increase in Reynolds number.

It is observed that as Re increase from 200 to 500 at $X=5.74H$, there is 91% increase in Nusselt number. So the heat transfer enhances with the increase in Reynolds number.

Figure 5.7 Variation of bulk temperature

5.4 VALIDATION

The present discretization scheme can be tested by taking the model problem of flow in a lid driven square cavity with the two dimensional computational domain and same boundary conditions are taken as in [25]. The U velocity components at the vertical mid plane of square cavity for Re=400 are found to be in good agreement with results of Ghia.et.al [25].

6 CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

6.1 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In the present problem, the numerical simulation of laminar flow with a rectangular winglet and a rectangular winglet pair in a rectangular channel has been performed at Reynolds number =200 and $\beta=28.7^\circ$ by solving the three dimensional, unsteady, incompressible Navier Stroke equations and the energy equation using modified MAC method.

With the mentioned computations in mind we are now in position to say that the heat transfer enhancement is more with the use of vortex generator leading to more compact heat exchanger as compared to plain channel flow with associated increase in pumping power. It can be seen that about 90 percent enhancement of heat transfer can be achieved with the winglet pair at the expense of a moderate pressure drop as comparison to the plane channel flow. In conclusion it can be said that

1. The channel with a winglet pair is more effective as comparison to the single winglet.
2. The heat transfer increases with the increase of the winglet height.
3. The heat transfer increases with the increase in Reynolds number.

6.2 SCOPE FOR FURTHER WORK

The computation has been done assuming the flow regime to be laminar in plate heat exchangers. But in some special application involving high velocity of fluid, the flow regime can become turbulent. Therefore, the present study can be extended for the turbulent flows. Using an appropriate turbulence model, the performance of the purposed design can be computed for high Reynolds number. This study can also be extended for the finite thickness of the winglet pair.

REFERENCES

- 1. Shah, R.K, Fundamentals of Heat Exchanger Design, John Wiley & Sons, Inc.**
New York, 2002
- 2. Kays, W.M. and London, A.L.** Compact heat exchangers, 3rd Ed. Krieger Publ. Co., Florida, 1998.
- 3. Anderson Dale A., Tannehill John C.,** Computational Fluid Mechanics and Heat Transfer. Hemispheres, Taylor & Francis, 1997.
- 4. Webb, R.L.** Principal of Enhanced Heat Transfer, John Wiley, New York, 1994.
- 5. Jacoabi, A.M. and Shah, R.K.** Heat transfer surface enhancement through the use of longitudinal vortices: a review of recent progress. *Exp. Thermal fluid Sci.*, 1995, **11**,295-309.
- 6. Fiebig, M. and Mitra, N.K** Flow structure and Heat transfer in channels with wing type Vortex Generators. *Notes on Numerical Fluid Mechanics.* 1984, **40**, 257-264.
- 7. Biswas, G, and Chattopadhyay, H.** Heat transfer in a channel with built-in wing-type vortex generators. *International Journal of Heat and Mass transfer.* 1992, **35**, 803-814.
- 8. Biswas, G., Mitra, N.K. and Fiebig, M.** Heat transfer enhancement in fin-tube heat Exchangers by winglet type vortex generators. *International Journal of Heat & Mass transfer.* 1994, **37**, 283-291.
- 9. Deb, P., Biswas, G. and Mitra.N.K.** Heat transfer and flow structure in laminar and turbulent flows in a rectangular channel with longitudinal vortices. *International Journal of Heat and Mass transfer.* 1995, **38**, 2427-2444.
- 10. Gentry, M.C. And Jacobi, A.M.** Heat Transfer Enhancement by Delta-Wing Vortex Generators on a Flat Plate, Vortex Interactions with the Boundary Layer. *Journal of Heat transfer.* 1997, **49**, 231-242.
- 11. Chen, Y., Fiebig, M. and Mitra, N.K.** Conjugate heat transfer of a finned oval tube with a punched longitudinal vortex generator in form of a delta winglet-parametric investigations of the winglet. *International journal of Heat and Mass transfer.* 1998, **42**, 3961-3978.
- 12. Vasudevan, R., Eswaran, V. and Biswas, G.** Winglet-type vortex generators for plate fin heat exchangers using triangular fins. *Journal of Numerical Heat transfer.* 2000, **58**, 533-555.
- 13. Torri, K., Kwak, K.M. and Nishino, K.** Heat transfer enhancement accompanying pressure-loss reduction with winglet-type vortex generators for fin-tube heat exchanger, *International Journal of Heat and Mass transfer.*, 2002, **45**, 3795-3801.

About the Author -

Prashant Kumar is an M.Tech (Thermal Engineering) student in Jagannath Gupta Institute of Engineering & Technology (JNIT) University, Jaipur. His area of expertise is Thermal Engineering and his research concerns the Numerical Analysis of Heat Transfer Enhancement in channel Flow. He is doing M.Tech in Thermal Engineering from the Jagannath Gupta Institute of Engineering & Technology.